

Original article

Analysis of fat oxidation capacity during cardiopulmonary exercise testing indicates long-lasting metabolic disturbance in patients with post-covid-19 syndrome

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SUMMARY

Background & aims: Post-COVID-19 Syndrome (PCS) is characterized by symptoms including fatigue, reduced physical performance, dyspnea, cognitive impairment, and psychological distress. The mechanisms underlying the onset and severity of PCS point to mitochondrial dysfunction as significant contributor. This study examined fat oxidation as a function of mitochondrial capacity during exercise. **Methods:** Single-center prospective cohort study during inpatient rehabilitation. Cardiopulmonary exercise testing and assessment of fatigue using questionnaires were performed at admission and discharge. Detailed spirometric breath-by-breath data were used to calculate substrate oxidation rates. **Results:** Patients (N = 187; 38 % women; 49.7 ± 11.4 years) were referred to rehabilitation 253.4 ± 130.6 days after infection. Lead symptoms included fatigue/exercise intolerance (79.9 %), shortness of breath (77.0 %), and cognitive dysfunction (55.1 %). Fat oxidation capacity was disturbed in PCS patients overall (AUC: 11.3 [10.7–11.9]) compared to healthy controls (p < 0.0001), with hospitalization during acute infection predicting the level of disturbance (p < 0.0001). Low exercise capacity and high fatigue scores resulted in reduced fat oxidation (both p < 0.0001). In particular, younger males were affected by significantly reduced fat oxidation capacity (sex: p = 0.002; age: p < 0.001). Metabolic disturbance was significantly improved during exercise-based rehabilitation (AUC: 14.9 [14.4–15.4]; p < 0.0001), even for the group of younger impaired males (+44.2 %; p < 0.0001). Carbohydrate oxidation was not impaired. **Conclusions:** PCS-specific restrictions in fat oxidation may indicate persistent mitochondrial dysfunction. Clinical assessment of PCS patients should include detailed breath-by-breath analysis during exercise to identify metabolic alterations especially in the group of younger males identified in this report. Exercise-based rehabilitation results in improved exercise capacity and fat oxidation and thus likely mitochondrial function. Clinical Trials: NCT06468722.

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1. Introduction

Post-COVID-19 Syndrome (PCS), also known as post-acute sequelae of COVID-19, manifests following an acute infection with the SARS-CoV-2 virus (COVID-19 infection). PCS is characterized by the persistence of symptoms beyond 12 weeks from the onset of infection and/or the emergence of new symptoms within this time [1]. Although recent guidelines offer specific criteria to diagnose PCS [1,2], ambiguity persists due to the complex nature of its

symptomatology and the lack of definitive diagnostic tools [3]. PCS is a multisystemic disorder characterized by symptoms such as (chronic) fatigue, diminished physical performance, muscular weakness and pain, dyspnea, cognitive impairments and alterations of the autonomous nervous system, as well as mental and psychological distress [2–6]. The severity of symptoms varies widely among patients, from mild impairment to significant restrictions in daily activities, potentially leading to partial or complete incapacity to work [2,3]. Of note, the severity of the acute infection does not predict the onset or severity of PCS [1,7]. Despite ongoing investigations, the mechanisms contributing to the onset and severity of PCS remain largely unknown. Factors may include endothelial dysfunction and detrimental effects on the

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microvasculature, as well as a “cytokine storm” associated with excessive oxidative stress and subsequent mitochondrial dysfunction which has emerged as a significant potential contributor [8–10]. Notably, detrimental effects on mitochondrial function have been described as a result of severe acute infections triggering an excessive immune response, systemic inflammation and oxidative stress [11]. Recent studies suggested that impaired mitochondrial function in PCS may be associated with impaired fatty acid oxidation (FatOx) which can be identified using cardiopulmonary exercise testing (CPET) [12,13].

Currently, the number of PCS patients characterized for changes in FatOx using CPET is low and associations with signs and symptoms of PCS such as fatigue have not been reported in detail. Even though rehabilitation programs have been shown to induce significant improvements in exercise capacity [14–18] as well as higher quality of life, reduced fatigue, and less depression [14–16], reports on the potential of exercise-based rehabilitation to restore FatOx capacity in PCS are not available. Thus, the current study aimed to investigate if analysis of breath-by-breath spirometric data followed by an estimation of individual FatOx capacity can be used for the stratification of PCS patients. We hypothesized that a lower FatOx potential would be associated with PCS-specific signs and symptoms such as mental and physical fatigue. In addition, we sought to analyze if exercise-based rehabilitation would be effective in restoring PCS patients' FatOx capacity as a sign of improved mitochondrial function.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Study design

A prospective observational cohort study of PCS patients referred for inpatient medical rehabilitation at Clinic Königfeld, Germany was performed between April 2021 and June 2023. Inclusion criteria were a history of (at least one) COVID-19 infection (positive PCR test at the time of infection), and ongoing or newly expressed performance deficits lasting for at least 3 months prior to recruitment as defined in the S1 guidelines [1]. Patients with the indication of inability to work, symptom and disease burden and associated restriction in everyday life were eligible. Patients with full clinical assessment and valid symptom-limited CPET at enrollment were analyzed for individual FatOx capacity based on breath-by-breath spirometric data. Patients with coronary artery disease (CAD) undergoing guideline-based medical rehabilitation were used as controls. Performance deficits were documented according to the recent consensus statement, with the cluster of lead symptoms including fatigue/exercise intolerance, shortness of breath, and cognitive dysfunction [5]. In addition, fatigue was quantified using the Multidimensional Fatigue Inventory [19], which provides an aggregate score and two subscales pertaining to physical and mental fatigue (Scores range from 0 to 100, with higher values indicating elevated levels of fatigue). History of comorbidities and current medication were documented, and blood samples for full blood count were drawn on the day of admission and sent to reference laboratory for analysis.

2.2. Ethical approval

The study was approved by the local ethical review committee (Ethik-Kommission Universität Witten/Herdecke; reference number 159/2021 and 115/2020 for PCS and CAD patients, respectively) and conformed to the Declaration of Helsinki. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants.

2.3. Controls

Two different controls were used for the present study. A) For comparison of individual FatOx capacity based on breath-by-breath spirometric data, data from CAD patients (N = 233) recruited during the observational period were used as control. CAD patients after acute myocardial infarction and/or reperfusion via percutaneous transluminal coronary angioplasty referred to medical rehabilitation were included. A detailed clinical workup including comorbidities, medication was available for this group. B) Published data from different cohorts analyzed for FatOx capacity using the identical approach was identified by literature search. Data on the cohort characteristics (health status, age, sex, fat free body mass [where available], and number of participants) as well as the mean and SD of maximal fat oxidation (MFO) was extracted and statistically compared to PCS and CAD patients.

2.4. Cardiopulmonary exercise testing (CPET)

Symptom-limited ergometer testing with continuous breath-by-breath respiratory gas exchange analysis was conducted following manufacturer's guidelines (Ergostic, Amedtec, Aue, Germany) as part of the standard clinical diagnostic procedure upon admission and within three days prior to discharge as described [16]. Expiratory flow measurements were performed using a mass flow sensor, calibrated with a known concentration gas mixture prior to each assessment. The initial assessment of physical fitness was conducted through a cardiac stress ECG, and a tailored ramp protocol was selected for CPET based on the results as follows: 1. for low performance (< 100 W), initiation at 20 W with increments of 15 W every 2 min; 2. for medium performance (100–125 W), initiation at 20 W with increments of 20 W every 2 min; 3. for moderate performance (> 125 W), initiation at 25 W with increments of 25 W every 2 min. All CPETs were performed non-fasting in the morning at the same time of the day using the identical protocol for each individual patient at admission and before discharge. There were no restrictions regarding food intake or training the day before CPET as patients followed their standardized in-house balanced diet and exercise routines. Continuously recorded variables included workload (W), heart rate (HR), oxygen consumption (VO₂), carbon dioxide production (VCO₂), and minute ventilation (VE). N = 187 CPETs were available at admission, N = 164 before discharge (23 examinations not performed due to scheduling problems). Participants were instructed to achieve a rating of perceived exertion (RPE) of ≥ 8 on the 0–10 Borg Scale during the test. The Ergostic system was additionally used for measurements of resting metabolic rates (N = 127 available). In brief, measurements were performed in the morning, in a quiet room (20 ± 2 °C) in supine position after an overnight fast.

2.5. Calculation of fat oxidation from CPET data

Spirometric breath-by-breath data from CPET were resolved second by second using the MATLAB (vR2019b, MathWorks Inc., Natick, USA) function “synchronize” followed by linear interpolation using the “retime” function. Continuously interpolated VO₂ and VCO₂ data were used to calculate fat oxidation (FatOx) and carbohydrate oxidation (ChOx) using the stoichiometric equations of Frayn and colleagues [20], with the assumption that the urinary nitrogen excretion rate was negligible [21], which were then plotted as percentage of peak VO₂. In order to exclude an effect of fat-free mass (FFM), analyses were also performed with fat oxidation normalized to individual FFM. Subgroups were built for sex, age, hospitalization during/time after acute infection, lead symptoms, fatigue score (quartiles using median split) and exercise

capacity at admission of rehabilitation. Exercise capacity is indicated as absolute oxygen consumption at peak exercise (VO_{2peak} , ml O_2 /min) or as relative exercise capacity (percent of reference) corrected for sex, age and body surface.

2.6. Statistical analysis

Data was analyzed using SPSS (V.28, IBM, Armonk, USA) and GraphPad Prism (V.10, GraphPad Software, Boston, USA). Constant variables are expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD) or 95 % CI. Categorical variables are presented as n (%). Differences between groups (quartiles) were analyzed using one-factorial ANOVA, unpaired two-sided t-test or Mann-Whitney U test in case of non-normal distribution. Non-normal distribution was tested using skewness and kurtosis. Chi-square test was used for categorical variables. Spearman rank correlation analyses were performed to investigate correlations between FatOx, physical exercise capacity and fatigue. CPET-derived FatOx trend lines were modelled using asymmetrical five-parameter dose-response curve fit and 95 % CI. Area under the curve (AUC) was calculated as described and indicated with respective 95 % CI [22]. Linear regression slopes of data were produced using FatOx from start to peak including F statistics. MFO data from published articles was compared to MFO (mean of individual maximal fat oxidation) from PCS and CAD patients using one-way ANOVA. Statistical significance was accepted at $p < 0.05$.

3. Results

3.1. General observations

PCS Patients (N = 187; 38 % women) were referred to rehabilitation with an average age of 49.7 ± 11.4 years, and a mean time interval between first infection and start of medical rehabilitation of 253.4 ± 130.6 days (Table 1). Fatigue/exercise intolerance and shortness of breath were observed in ~80 % of patients, while cognitive dysfunction was less common (~55 %). During the acute phase of infection, 72.2 % of patients received ambulant care or acute care at home, while 27.8 % of patients required in-hospital care. Overall, patients reported a high frequency of endocrine, nutritional, and metabolic disorders, as well as circulatory system disorders and exercise capacity was significantly reduced compared to reference (Table 2). Results of blood analyses were within the reference range (data not shown). Overall, 34.8 % of patients were ever smoker.

3.2. Impaired FatOx in PCS patients

To investigate beta oxidation rates of PCS patients at the time of admission, CPET was performed and FatOx was calculated using breath-by-breath data over time. Compared to healthy individuals [23–25], PCS patients exhibited a notable impairment in FatOx at an identical low level as patients with CAD (Fig. 1A; Supplemental Table 1). FatOx over time in PCS patients was marked by a low mean peak value and a steep decrease after peak ($Y = 0.003908 * X + 0.1539$) and an area under the curve (AUC) of 11.3 (95 % CI, 10.7–11.9). Maximal fat oxidation (MFO) in PCS patients (0.35 ± 0.12 g/min) was significantly lower compared to moderately trained (0.52 ± 0.15 g/min) [26] and healthy adults (0.46 ± 0.17 g/min; both $p \leq 0.0001$) [24], while restriction in MFO was comparable to patients with type 2 diabetes (0.28 ± 0.07 g/min) [27] and older individuals with mild cognitive impairment (0.31 ± 0.13 g/min) [28] (Fig. 1B). Of note, PCS patients exhibited similar restriction in FatOx and MFO compared to patients with CAD (AUC = 12.2 [11.7–12.8], MFO = 0.33 ± 0.14 g/min), despite being 5 years younger (PCS, 49.7 ± 11.4 ; CAD, 55.5 ± 7.5).

Table 1
Anthropometric and clinical data.

	Overall N = 187
Anthropometric data	
Age, years	49.7 \pm 11.4
Sex, n (%)	
Female	71 (38)
Male	116 (62)
Height, cm	174.5 \pm 9.1
Weight, kg	91.4 \pm 21.1
BMI, kg·m ⁻²	29.9 \pm 6.0
Body Fat Mass, kg	31.3 \pm 13.7
Soft Lean Mass, kg	56.9 \pm 11.7
(Post-) COVID-19 Characteristics	
Acute care during infection	
Ambulant care	135 (72.2)
Hospitalized, w/o ventilation	29 (15.5)
Hospitalized, with ventilation	23 (12.3)
Time between acute infection and rehabilitation start	
Lead symptoms at rehabilitation start	253.4 \pm 130.6
Fatigue/exercise intolerance	149 (79.7)
Shortness of breath	144 (77.0)
Cognitive dysfunction	103 (55.1)
Comorbidities	
Endocrine, nutritional or metabolic diseases	
Obesity	119 (63.6)
Hyperlipidemia	79 (42.2)
Type 2 diabetes mellitus	25 (13.4)
Hypothyroidism	21 (11.2)
Other	14 (7.5)
Other	29 (15.5)
Diseases of the circulatory system	
Arterial hypertension	118 (63.1)
Other	90 (48.1)
Other	53 (28.3)
Diseases of the musculoskeletal system and connective tissue	
Other	67 (35.8)
Diseases of the nervous system	
Mental and behavioral disorders	47 (25.1)
Depressive/adjustment disorders	39 (20.9)
Other	23 (12.3)
Other	18 (9.6)
Diseases of the respiratory system	
Other	26 (13.9)
Diseases of the digestive system	
Other	20 (10.7)
Neoplasms	
Other	10 (5.3)
Medication	
Beta blocker	58 (31.0)
Analgesic	43 (23.0)
AT-II receptor blocker	38 (20.3)
Anticoagulant	37 (19.8)
ACE inhibitor	33 (17.6)
Calcium channel blocker	31 (16.6)
Diuretic	31 (16.6)
Statin	30 (16.0)
Glucocorticoid	28 (15.0)
Antidepressant	21 (11.2)
Diabetes medication	9 (4.8)
Antiarrhythmic	2 (1.1)

Data is presented as mean \pm SD or n (%). Diseases/symptoms with a prevalence <5 % are not reported.

Comparisons with CAD patients, healthy controls and diabetic patients appeared unaffected by FFM. Stratification by age quartiles revealed that limited FatOx was predominantly seen in patients with younger age (≤ 43 years, AUC = 8.2, Fig. 1D), with a significantly reduced slope from start to peak ($p \leq 0.0001$). Differences between female and male PCS patients were nonexistent after correction for FFM (Supplemental Fig. 1). In contrast, leg lean mass had no effect on differences in FatOx. Of note, FatOx rates showed larger reduction in patients who were hospitalized during their acute COVID-19 infection compared to patients receiving ambulant care (AUC = 10.6 vs. 11.6). There were no signs of reduced FatOx with the presence of lead symptoms fatigue/exercise intolerance, shortness of breath, and cognitive dysfunction (Fig. 2A-C). However, the detailed examination of fatigue using

Table 2
Exercise capacity assessed by cardiopulmonary exercise capacity (CPET).

	Pre		Post	
	absolute	% predicted	absolute	% predicted
Resting				
Heart rate, beat·min ⁻¹	88.3 ± 11.9	n.a.	83.9 ± 11.0*	n.a.
O ₂ pulse, ml·beat ⁻¹	6.7 ± 1.7	n.a.	6.8 ± 1.5	n.a.
Ventilatory equivalent O ₂ (VE/VO ₂)	28.1 ± 7.4	n.a.	27.7 ± 5.9	n.a.
Ventilatory equivalent CO ₂ (VE/VCO ₂)	33.6 ± 5.7	n.a.	33.9 ± 4.4	n.a.
Ventilatory threshold 1 (VT1)				
Workload, watt	71.2 ± 25.6	41.5 ± 14.2	83.2 ± 28.0*	49.4 ± 17.0
Heart rate, beat·min ⁻¹	107.9 ± 15.0	64.8 ± 8.1	107.3 ± 19.3	64.6 ± 10.5
O ₂ pulse, ml·beat ⁻¹	10.4 ± 2.8	76.2 ± 16.2	11.1 ± 2.9*	82.2 ± 17.4
VO ₂ , ml·min ⁻¹ ·kg ⁻¹	12.1 ± 3.1	49.2 ± 11.7	13.2 ± 3.9*	53.8 ± 13.0
Ventilatory equivalent O ₂ (VE/VO ₂)	27.6 ± 5.5	79.0 ± 15.7	26.8 ± 4.3*	76.6 ± 12.1
Ventilatory equivalent CO ₂ (VE/VCO ₂)	30.9 ± 5.2	n.a.	29.7 ± 4.2*	n.a.
Respiratory minute ventilation (VE), l·min ⁻¹	32.9 ± 9.1	32.1 ± 8.0	34.2 ± 8.6	33.7 ± 8.4
Tidal volume (Vt), l	1.6 ± 0.6	55.4 ± 19.8	1.8 ± 0.6*	61.5 ± 19.2
Breathing frequency (Bf), breaths·min ⁻¹	22.0 ± 6.6	39.9 ± 12.0	20.5 ± 5.9*	37.3 ± 10.6
Breathing reserve (BR), %	66.3 ± 12.7	n.a.	65.7 ± 11.1	n.a.
Peak exercise (VO_{2peak})				
Respiratory exchange rate (RER)	1.05 ± 0.1	87.2 ± 8.4	1.06 ± 0.1	87.4 ± 6.9
Workload, watt	125.0 ± 35.8	72.2 ± 20.3	135.2 ± 44.1*	79.8 ± 25.0
Heart rate, beat·min ⁻¹	133.7 ± 21.2	80.4 ± 11.6	132.2 ± 21.5	79.6 ± 11.6
O ₂ pulse, ml·beat ⁻¹	12.4 ± 3.1	91.7 ± 17.0	13.0 ± 3.4*	96.3 ± 18.9
VO ₂ , ml·min ⁻¹ ·kg ⁻¹	18.1 ± 4.6	73.1 ± 15.5	18.8 ± 5.2*	76.2 ± 16.8
Ventilatory equivalent O ₂ (VE/VO ₂)	34.2 ± 6.6	97.9 ± 18.8	33.7 ± 5.7	96.3 ± 16.5
Ventilatory equivalent CO ₂ (VE/VCO ₂)	32.5 ± 5.5	n.a.	31.9 ± 4.8	n.a.
Respiratory minute ventilation (VE), l·min ⁻¹	58.9 ± 14.4	58.1 ± 14.6	60.3 ± 16.4	59.3 ± 14.9
Tidal volume (Vt), l	2.1 ± 0.6	72.7 ± 21.6	2.2 ± 0.6*	75.3 ± 20.1
Breathing frequency (Bf), breaths·min ⁻¹	29.5 ± 7.8	53.6 ± 14.1	28.6 ± 6.7	52.0 ± 12.1
Breathing reserve (BR), %	40.6 ± 17.7	n.a.	40.7 ± 16.9	n.a.

Data is presented as mean ± SD, at admission (Pre) and discharge (Post). Changes over time were analyzed with absolute values using paired two-sided t-test or Wilcoxon test.

* Significantly different from Pre to Post.

the MFI-20 questionnaire showed that patients with higher fatigue levels had stronger restriction in FatOx (AUC = 9.9 vs. ≥12.1; Fig. 2D). Of note, this was seen for both, mental and physical fatigue, while the strongest restriction of FatOx was seen in the group of patients with very high physical fatigue (MFI-20_p ≥ 95 [of 100], AUC = 9.3) (Fig. 2E and F). Linear regression slopes to peak were significantly different for overall, as well as for mental and physical fatigue (all $p \leq 0.0001$).

3.3. Stratification using FatOx analysis

Since FatOx depends on exercise capacity, quartiles for absolute exercise capacity were generated. As expected, higher absolute exercise capacity (L O₂/min) was associated with higher peak FatOx ($r = 0.407$, $p \leq 0.0001$) (Fig. 3A). Linear regression to peak differed significantly, with steeper slopes for quartiles with higher absolute exercise capacity ($p < 0.0001$) and non-overlapping 95 % CIs for AUC. Subsequently, known factors affecting exercise capacity in general were used for adjustment and relative exercise capacity corrected for sex, age and body surface area was used to analyze relative FatOx. This approach identified a group with aberrant restriction in FatOx (Fig. 3B). Linear regression to peak was significantly different and AUC was lowest in this group ($p \leq 0.0001$; AUC = 8.6 vs. ≥12.1). Characterization of this group (Table 3) revealed a significantly larger proportion of younger men compared to the other quartiles (79.2 % vs. 56.1 %, $p = 0.006$; 44.4 ± 13.7 years vs. 51.6 ± 9.9 years; $p = 0.001$). Hospitalization during acute infection, time interval between acute infection and start of rehabilitation and the presence of lead symptoms at start of rehabilitation did not differ between the groups (Fig. 3 B₁/B₂, Table 3). Of note, analysis of resting metabolic rates did not reveal a difference in fat or carbohydrate oxidation, which was confirmed

after adjusting for gender, weight and muscle mass (all $p \geq 0.05$), indicating that FatOx is mainly restricted during exercise. Serum lipid levels (triglycerides, total cholesterol, HDL and LDL cholesterol) did not significantly differ between both groups.

3.4. Improving FatOx by exercise-based rehabilitation

To investigate the effects of exercise-based rehabilitation on FatOx rates, CPET data before and after ~4 weeks was compared. During a mean of 28.9 ± 6.6 days, patients performed on average 12 exercise-based therapy sessions per week consisting of a combination of strength and endurance training, such as exercise in groups, aerobic ergometer training, medical training therapy, aqua fitness, walking and circuit training (whole-body strength endurance and aerobic endurance training with light equipment or body weight) as described [29]. FatOx significantly improved seen in higher peak oxidation rates ($p = 0.0025$) and an overall shift of the FatOx curve (Fig. 4), represented by a slope of $Y = 0.004935 \cdot X + 0.1761$ and higher AUC of 14.9 (95 % CI, 14.4–15.4) corresponding to an improvement of ~31.9 %. This improvement from baseline to follow-up was highest for the patient group with the lowest relative baseline FatOx rates, in that an overall ~45 % increase was detected, indicated by a change in AUC from 8.6 (95 % CI, 8.0–9.2) to 12.4 (95 % CI, 11.9–12.9) and a significantly enhanced peak oxidation rate (pre, 0.186 g/min vs. post, 0.254 g/min, $p \leq 0.0001$) (Fig. 4). All findings, except for the differences in sex, were independent of fat-free mass (Supplemental Figs. 1–3). Of note, and in line with a previous report [12], overall ChOx was not impaired in PCS patients, showed comparably low inter-individual variability, and neither hospitalization, time after infection and lead symptoms affected ChOx (Supplemental Fig. 4). Medical

Fig. 1. Disturbed fat oxidation is aggravated in long-term patients with Post-COVID-19 syndrome (PCS) with a history of hospitalization during acute infection. Continuous β -oxidation of fatty acids was calculated by stoichiometric equations [19] using individual breath-by-breath data during cardiopulmonary exercise testing (CPET) of PCS patients at admission of rehabilitation. **A)** Fat oxidation over exercise intensity [percentage of VO_{2peak}] is given for PCS patients (N = 187) and patients with coronary artery disease (CAD, N = 233) used as control. **B)** Maximal fat oxidation (MFO) of PCS patients compared to patients with CAD, individuals with mild cognitive impairment (MCI) [26], patients with type 2 diabetes (T2D) [25] as well as healthy and moderately trained adults [22,24]. For comparability with published data, mean and SD of MFO were calculated from individual maximal fat oxidation values. Respective publications given in the table (left to right). PCS patients' fat oxidation over exercise intensity [percentage of VO_{2peak}] was categorized by **C)** sex (female, N = 71; male, N = 116), **D)** age quartiles (≤ 43 years, N = 48; 44–53 years, N = 47; 54–59 years, N = 56; ≥ 60 years, N = 36), **E)** hospitalization during acute infection (hospitalized, N = 52; ambulant care, N = 135), and **F)** time quartiles after acute infection (≤ 156 days, N = 47; 157–225 days, N = 48; 226–323 days, N = 46; ≥ 324 days, N = 46). Data is presented as mean of individual data points (with 95 % confidence interval [CI] in panel A). Lower and Upper 95 % CI: C) female, 0.034–0.051; male, 0.108–0.123; D) 43 years, 0.018–0.037; 44–53 years, 0.075–0.091; 54–59 years, 0.125–0.138; ≥ 60 years, 0.099–0.114; E) ambulant, 0.079–0.096; hospitalized, 0.082–0.096; F) ≤ 156 days, 0.091–0.103; 157–225 days, 0.053–0.072; 226–323 days, 0.118–0.133; ≥ 324 days, 0.059–0.076. Trend line was modelled using asymmetrical five-parameter dose-response curve fit. Area under the curve (AUC) is indicated with respective 95 % CI. Insets show comparison of linear regressions slopes of data from start to peak with F statistics.

rehabilitation led to marginal improvements in ChOx likely explained by the overall improvement in exercise capacity.

4. Discussion

This study assessed the fat oxidation (FatOx) capacity of patients with long-term PCS using breath-by-breath spirometric data from cardiopulmonary exercise testing (CPET) before and after inpatient rehabilitation. In brief, the key findings of this study are that (1) FatOx capacity in long-term PCS patients is deteriorated, (2) hospitalization predicts the level of metabolic disturbance in terms of reduced FatOx capacity, (3) mental and physical fatigue were increased in PCS patients with reduced FatOx capacity, and (4) metabolic disturbance in terms of FatOx can be restored by exercise-based rehabilitation. In addition, the application of CPET-based screening identified a group of predominantly young male PCS patients with severe metabolic restrictions, who had the greatest benefit from exercise-based rehabilitation. To the best of our knowledge, this study is the first to describe deteriorated FatOx capacity in a larger cohort of long-term PCS patients (> 6 months)

and to show that exercise-based rehabilitation represents an effective intervention to restore FatOx capacity.

The PCS patients included in this study were referred to medical rehabilitation with a clinically relevant limitation in physical performance, a finding in line with previous reports [30–32]. This common finding has partly been attributed to mitochondrial dysfunction and several studies have provided evidence that the SARS-CoV-2 virus may induce metabolic reprogramming and virus particles may interfere with mitochondrial functioning [33,34]. A recent pilot study suggested that impaired mitochondrial function in PCS patients may be demonstrated by detection of reduced FatOx capacity during CPET [12]. Here, we used detailed breath-by-breath analysis in a well-characterized PCS cohort and compared the FatOx potential to patients with CAD and published data from patients with metabolic disease and mild cognitive decline as well as healthy controls. PCS patients showed significantly impaired fat oxidation capacity compared to healthy and moderately trained individuals, while impairment was comparable to patients with CAD, mild cognitive impairment or type 2 diabetes. Thus, our results not only

Fig. 2. Deteriorated fat oxidation is aggravated in PCS patients with higher physical fatigue. Continuous β -oxidation of fatty acids was calculated using individual breath-by-breath data during cardiopulmonary exercise testing (CPET) and grouped by presence of lead symptoms and fatigue scores at admission. **A)** fatigue/exercise intolerance (non-existent, N = 38; present, N = 149), **B)** shortness of breath (non-existent, N = 43; present, N = 144), **C)** cognitive dysfunction (non-existent, N = 84; present, N = 103), **D)** β -oxidation by MFI-20 overall fatigue score quartiles (≤ 63 , N = 44; 64–72, N = 41; 73–80, N = 42; ≥ 81 , N = 39); **E)** MFI-20 mental fatigue score quartiles (≤ 50 , N = 45; 55–70, N = 47; 75–80, N = 34; ≥ 85 , N = 40) and **F)** MFI-20 physical fatigue score quartiles (≤ 70 , N = 58; 75–80, N = 42; 85–90, N = 33; ≥ 95 , N = 33). Data is presented as mean of individual data points. Lower and Upper 95 % CI: A) non-existent, 0.085–0.102; present, 0.079–0.094; B) non-existent, 0.048–0.065; present, 0.090–0.105; C) non-existent, 0.074–0.091; present, 0.085–0.100; D) ≤ 63 , 0.076–0.095; 64–72, 0.096–0.111; 73–80, 0.090–0.105; ≥ 81 , 0.063–0.078; E) ≤ 50 , 0.078–0.097; 55–70, 0.081–0.096; 75–80, 0.112–0.128; ≥ 85 , 0.059–0.075; F) ≤ 70 , 0.075–0.094; 75–80, 0.096–0.111; 85–90, 0.092–0.109; ≥ 95 , 0.063–0.076. Trend line was modelled using asymmetrical five-parameter dose-response curve fit. Area under the curve (AUC) is indicated with respective 95 % CI. Insets show comparison of linear regressions slopes of data from start to peak with F statistics. MFI-20, Multidimensional Fatigue Inventory (N = 166 available, score 0–100, higher values = higher fatigue).

Fig. 3. Analysis of fat oxidation rates during cardiopulmonary exercise testing (CPET) identifies middle-aged male PCS patients with significant impairment of β -oxidation. Continuous β -oxidation of fatty acids was calculated using individual breath-by-breath data during CPET and grouped by **A)** absolute exercise capacity (O_2 L/min) quartiles (≤ 1.37 L/min, N = 49; 1.38–1.58 L/min, N = 45; 1.59–1.89 L/min, N = 47; ≥ 1.90 L/min, N = 46), and **B)** relative exercise capacity quartiles after correction for sex, age, and body surface area (≤ 60 % of reference, N = 48; 61–71 % of reference, N = 48; 72–86 % of reference, N = 45; ≥ 87 % of reference, N = 46). Exercise capacity was defined as the peak oxygen uptake (VO_{2peak}). Data is presented as mean of individual data points. Lower and Upper 95 % CI: A) ≤ 1.37 L/min, 0.028–0.040; 1.38–1.58 L/min, 0.074–0.090; 1.59–1.89 L/min, 0.101–0.118; ≥ 1.90 L/min, 0.119–0.138; B) ≤ 60 % of reference, 0.061–0.073; 61–71 % of reference, 0.089–0.105; 72–86 % of reference, 0.098–0.112; ≥ 87 % of reference, 0.073–0.094. Trend line was modelled using asymmetrical five-parameter dose-response curve fit. Area under the curve (AUC) is indicated with respective 95 % CI. Insets show comparison of linear regressions slopes of data from start to peak with F statistics. **B₁** and **B₂**) Characteristics of PCS patients with lowest fat oxidation rates after stratification identifies a high percentage of middle-aged males. Data is presented as mean \pm SD or n (%).

Table 3
Differences of anthropometric and clinical data between quartiles of relative exercise capacity.

	1st Quartile (N = 48) AUC: 8.6 (8.0–9.2)	2nd Quartile (N = 48) AUC: 12.1 (11.5–12.7)	3rd Quartile (N = 45) AUC: 12.2 (11.6–12.8)	4th Quartile (N = 46) AUC: 12.6 (12.1–13.0)	2nd – 4th Quartile (N = 139)	p-value
Anthropometric data						
Age, years	44.4 ± 13.7 #§§	51.7 ± 9.8	51.0 ± 9.5	52.1 ± 10.4	51.6 ± 9.9	0.002
Sex, n (%)						<0.001
Female	10 (20.8) §§	8 (16.7)	23 (51.1)	30 (65.2)	61 (43.9)	
Male	38 (79.2) §§	40 (83.3)	22 (48.9)	16 (34.8)	78 (56.1)	
Height, cm	176.1 ± 9.8	177.7 ± 7.7	172.6 ± 9.2	171.4 ± 8.3	174.0 ± 8.8	0.002
Weight, kg	91.2 ± 25.4	96.6 ± 17.8	93.5 ± 23.1	84.3 ± 14.9	91.5 ± 19.5	0.033
BMI, kg·m ⁻²	29.2 ± 6.7	30.5 ± 5.2	31.2 ± 6.6	28.7 ± 5.0	30.2 ± 5.7	0.145
Body Fat Mass, kg	30.2 ± 16.0	32.1 ± 11.7	34.8 ± 14.6	28.3 ± 11.4	31.7 ± 12.8	0.134
Soft Lean Mass, kg	57.8 ± 12.5	61.3 ± 9.6	55.8 ± 12.2	52.7 ± 10.8	56.6 ± 11.4	0.004
(Post-) COVID-19 Characteristics						
Acute care during infection						
Ambulant care	35 (72.9) §	31 (64.6)	28 (62.2)	41 (89.1)	100 (71.9)	0.017
Hospitalized, w/o ventilation	6 (12.5)	11 (22.9)	7 (15.6)	5 (10.9)	23 (16.5)	0.379
Hospitalized, with ventilation	7 (14.6) §	6 (12.5)	10 (22.2)	0 (0)	16 (11.5)	0.013
Time between acute infection and rehabilitation start	253.3 ± 136.0	239.0 ± 119.0	239.3 ± 130.0	282.5 ± 136.4	253.5 ± 129.2	0.337
Lead symptoms at rehabilitation start						
Fatigue/exercise intolerance	42 (87.5)	38 (79.2)	37 (82.2)	32 (69.4)	107 (77.0)	0.181
Shortness of breath	38 (79.2)	37 (77.1)	33 (73.3)	36 (78.3)	106 (76.3)	0.917
Cognitive dysfunction	27 (56.3)	24 (50.0)	26 (57.8)	26 (56.5)	76 (54.7)	0.874
Fatigue/Exercise capacity						
Fatigue (MFI-20 score)	70.5 ± 12.8	70.2 ± 11.8	70.0 ± 16.3	69.7 ± 14.0	70.0 ± 14.0	0.995
Physical Fatigue	79.2 ± 13.5	76.3 ± 15.1	76.8 ± 18.7	77.0 ± 16.0	76.7 ± 16.5	0.848
Mental Fatigue	65.0 ± 20.1	67.7 ± 17.6	66.8 ± 22.3	67.5 ± 21.6	67.3 ± 20.4	0.930
Exercise capacity, VO ₂ , ml·min ⁻¹ ·kg ⁻¹	1.38 ± 0.33 #§§	1.67 ± 0.27	1.68 ± 0.43	1.82 ± 0.45	1.72 ± 0.39	<0.001
Blood lipids						
Triglycerides, mg/dL	185.7 ± 136.9	164.5 ± 89.5	178.3 ± 136.7	175.4 ± 210.0	172.6 ± 152.4	0.923
Cholesterol, mg/dL	202.9 ± 52.1	212.7 ± 42.5	218.2 ± 46.0	226.4 ± 54.2	219.1 ± 47.8	0.137
HDL cholesterol, mg/dL	52.3 ± 15.1	52.1 ± 15.4	56.8 ± 17.3	59.0 ± 15.3	55.9 ± 16.2	0.092
LDL cholesterol, mg/dL	131.0 ± 42.3	138.9 ± 36.4	142.1 ± 38.5	147.5 ± 46.5	142.8 ± 40.5	0.277

Data is presented as mean ± SD or n (%). Between-group comparison was performed using one-way ANOVA, Kruskal-Wallis-Test, Jonckheere-Terpstra-Test or Chi-square test. # Significantly different between 1st and 2nd quartile. § Significantly different between 1st and 3rd quartile. § Significantly different between 1st and 4th quartile.

substantiate previous findings [12,13] but provide evidence that metabolic disturbances might be larger in PCS patients experiencing pronounced mental and physical fatigue. Of note, our PCS patients did not show significant differences in respiratory function pointing towards a whole-body deterioration in exercise capacity with a concomitant reduction in FatOx capacity. In this regard, a reduction in mitochondrial function might lead to lower fractional O₂ extraction and impaired muscle oxidative capacity, and inflammation altering mitochondrial dynamics [35]. These changes result in reduced ATP production while still consuming excess oxygen, leading to increased production of reactive oxygen species, and further damage of cellular components [13]. Since fat oxidation capacity in general is lowered in individuals with reduced exercise capacity [23–25], it is of interest to investigate if deconditioning and associated metabolic disturbance develops with time of ongoing PCS. Our analysis showed that hospitalization during acute infection led to greater reduction in FatOx capacity and that time between acute infection and rehabilitation also affected FatOx potential. In addition, a group consisting predominantly of younger men was identified, which presented with significantly reduced FatOx capacity. This group did not differ from the overall group of PCS patients in terms of hospitalization and mean time after acute infection. This observation suggests that in addition to a gradual deconditioning over time, metabolic disturbance potentially caused by SARS-CoV-2-induced mitochondrial damage [34] may be the underlying cause in this group. While it could be speculated that these patients could have benefited from more intensive care during the acute phase of the infection, the exact mechanism of SARS-CoV-2 on metabolic function is unknown and could also occur in patients with

relatively mild acute infection. Of note, heart rate and O₂-pulse response during peak exercise were significantly restricted in this patient group, which may be associated with chronotropic intolerance caused by impaired energy metabolism and mitochondrial bioenergetics as a mechanism of impaired exercise intolerance [36].

The cellular changes involved in disturbed FatOx in PCS patients are not fully understood. Recent results from plasma metabolomics have revealed significantly higher concentrations of free- and carnitine-conjugated unsaturated fatty acids in PCS patients compared to healthy controls or individuals who fully recovered from COVID-19. These findings suggested altered fatty acid metabolism and impaired mitochondria-dependent lipid catabolism as well as impaired pyruvate/lactate metabolism in patients with PCS [37]. Elevated levels of fatty acids and acylcarnitines, including an increase in medium-chain fatty acids, suggest continuous mobilization of fatty acids combined with restricted oxidative capacity due to mitochondrial dysfunction, a pattern also observed in patients with type 2 diabetes and sepsis [37–39]. In addition, accumulation of free and carnitine-conjugated fatty acids in PCS has been associated with erythrocyte dysfunction, compromising oxygen delivery to target organs and impairing mitochondrial oxidative processes essential for fatty acids utilization [37,40]. Altered mitochondrial function and content has also been found in muscle biopsies of PCS patients along with histopathological changes including inflammatory infiltrates, signs of cell damage and impaired skeletal muscle O₂ utilization [35,41,42]. A recent report investigating the PCS plasma metabolome [43] found that markers of mitochondrial dysfunction indirectly reflecting the NADH/NAD + redox state, lipid metabolism, and ATP generation were associated with fatigue and muscular pain in PCS

Fig. 4. Exercise-based medical rehabilitation improves fat oxidation in patients with Post-COVID-19 syndrome (PCS). Continuous β -oxidation of fatty acids was calculated using individual breath-by-breath data during CPET and grouped by relative exercise capacity after correction for sex, age, and body surface area at baseline (BL) and follow-up (FU, before discharge). **A–C** An improvement in fat oxidation rates of $\sim 32\%$ was seen over all patients (baseline, $N = 187$; follow-up, $N = 164$). **D–F** PCS patients in the lowest quartile showed a considerably greater improvement of $\sim 44\%$ (baseline, $N = 48$; follow-up, $N = 40$). **G–I** PCS patients in the higher quartiles improved by $\sim 29\%$ (baseline, $N = 139$; follow-up, $N = 124$). Data is presented as mean of individual data points with 95 % CI. Trend line was modelled using asymmetrical five-parameter dose-response curve fit. Area under the curve (AUC) is indicated with respective 95 % CI. Insets show comparison of linear regressions slopes of data from start to peak with F statistics.

patients [43]. In addition, an increased ornithine/citrulline ratio has been reported, indicating abnormal metabolic activity in the urea cycle, which has also been reported in patients with chronic fatigue syndrome (CFS) [44]. Of note, intracellular accumulation of ammonia leads to inhibition of aerobic utilization of pyruvate in the TCA cycle, which may contribute further to fatigue [43]. It has been suggested that the observed long-term metabolic alterations in PCS may be directly linked to the pathobiology of SARS-CoV-2 with significant acute alterations in the metabolome, caused either by virus-induced mobilization of macromolecular building blocks such as nucleic acids, amino acids and fatty acids necessary for replication, or by the host responses to viral infection [37,40,45–47]. Although the implications of increased circulating free fatty acids on the functional manifestations of PCS remain uncertain, they are believed to facilitate viral particle formation during acute infection [40]. Guarneri et al. [48] recently showed that SARS-CoV-2 can block nuclear- and mitochondrial-encoded mitochondrial genes, inhibiting mitochondrial function in the heart, liver, kidneys, and lymph nodes, likely resulting in an energy deficit, compensated by a metabolic shift to glycolysis [49]. These metabolic abnormalities, particularly in fatty acids pathways, identified in hospitalized acute COVID-19 patients may persist in those with PCS [50–52]. Taken together, these findings support the hypothesis that a dysfunction in substrate utilization in mitochondria adds to the metabolic manifestations of PCS observed in this study. Evidence of impaired fat oxidation in PCS

patients during exercise might be indicative of mitochondrial damage and mitochondrial lipid catabolism inefficiency.

Some limitations to the present study may exist. Fat oxidation was assessed indirectly using pulmonary VO_2 and VCO_2 measured breath by breath, assuming that protein oxidation is negligible and constant. A direct measure of oxidative capacity such as blood lactate has not been included. Comparison of MFO with published data from different cohorts was limited as control groups were studied in a different setting. With respect to the reported results on maximal cardiopulmonary fitness, it needs to be considered that it is difficult to apply strict objective criteria for maximal exercise testing in PCS patients and results must therefore be interpreted with caution. It may be more suitable to perform submaximal exercise testing in PCS populations, also in view of the results reported here on disturbances in FatOx. It should also be noted that used ramp-graded exercise test used in this study for continuous calculation of FatOx and ChOx has not been validated using direct oxidation measurements in PCS patients. Additionally, it should be noted that FatOx is dependent on training status and therefore deconditioning could have additionally affect the observed impaired FatOx. Despite experiencing long-term symptoms, PCS patients enrolled in this study were capable to engage in exercise-based medical rehabilitation and our findings may not generalize to PCS patients experiencing more severe symptoms or presenting with different organ manifestations.

5. Conclusion

We conclude that PCS-specific restrictions in FatOx may be associated with typical symptoms such as exercise intolerance as well as mental and physical fatigue. Clinical assessment of PCS patients should include CPET with detailed breath-by-breath analysis, which represents an efficient tool to identify metabolic alterations. CPET-based assessment of FatOx capacity might be of considerable use in groups where PCS is considered less frequent such as the group of younger males not hospitalized during acute infection identified in this report. While exercise-based medical rehabilitation is recommended for eligible PCS patients in general, PCS patients with severely disturbed FatOx capacity might benefit largely from exercise, as it results in improved exercise capacity and fat oxidation and thus likely mitochondrial function.

Author contributions

Concept and design: B.S., F.C.M., R.G.; Patient recruitment: F.C.M., R.G.; Data Acquisition: R.G., H.S.; Data Processing: R.G., H.S.; Statistical analysis: R.G., B.S.; Drafting the article: R.G., B.S.; Critical revision: F.C.M.; All authors approval of the final version.

Data availability

Datasets used in this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clnu.2024.10.010>.

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